

FRACTURE CRITERIA FOR MULTIPLY CRACKED PIEZOELECTRIC MATERIALS

Jin H. Huang¹, Chieh-Hsuan Tsai¹, and Hsing-Chia Kuo²

¹*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Feng Chia University
Taichung 407, Taiwan, Republic of China*

²*Department of Naval Architecture & Marine Engineering, National Cheng-Kung University
Tainan 701, Taiwan, Republic of China*

SUMMARY: This study presents failure criteria for multiply permeable cracks embedded in an infinite piezoelectric solid, which is separately subjected to a set of uniform-electromechanical loads. Based on the equivalent inclusion method, permeable cracks are initially treated as elliptical inclusions with fictitious eigenstrains and eigenelectric fields, in which their elastic moduli and piezoelectric coefficients are taken as zero while dielectric constants remain finite. Consequently the interaction energy between the cracks and the applied electromechanical loading can be simply expressed in term of the applied electromechanical loads and the equivalent eigenfields. With this energy function, the energy release rates for fracture are separately acquired in a closed form for a simple tension, in-plane and out-plane shears, as well as normal electric flux density applied. The closed forms for energy release rates reveal that these forms are a function of the aspect ratio of the permeable elliptical cracks, type of the electromechanical loading, volume fraction of the cracks, and piezoelectric properties. Analysis results indicate that the different mechanical loading propagate the expansion of the elliptical cracks. Meanwhile, the distinct electric fields can retard the dilation of the elliptical cracks, particularly for an in-plane electric field incited perpendicular to the crack faces.

KEYWORDS: multiply permeable cracks, electromechanical loading, energy release rate.

INTRODUCTION

Recent works involving piezoelectric cracked materials have focused primarily on examining whether the materials contain a permeable or impermeable single crack. Parton [1] pioneered the analysis of piezoelectric crack problems from a fracture mechanics perspective. Although that investigation assumed that a slit crack in a piezoelectric solid is traction free, the electric potential and normal components of the electric displacement are permeably continuous across the cracked surface. In a related investigation, Deeg [2] proposed the method of distributed dislocations and electric dipoles to resolve an arbitrarily oriented slit crack with impermeable electric fields in a piezoelectric solid. Park [3, 4] employed a complex variable approach to examine the mode III crack problem in a piezoelectric solid and the in-plane

electrostatic fields in and around a circular piezoelectric inhomogeneity which was subjected to anti-plane loading. In addition, that investigation derived the stress and electric field intensity factors for different electroelastic loading, which is valid only for a circular inclusion. Suo et al. [5] investigated impermeable cracks in piezoelectric solids by employing Griffith's energy fracture mechanics to consider energetics due to electric and elastic effects. Their results demonstrated a number of cracking problems including strength of materials type solutions for two-dimensional cracks in homogeneous piezoelectrics and interfacial cracks in piezoelectric bimetals. They also derived Irwin-type relations connecting stress and electric field intensity factors with the energy release rate. Sosa [6] obtained asymptotic expressions for the coupled electroelastic fields at the tip of an impermeable crack in an infinite piezoelectric solid through a complex potential approach. In a related investigation, Dunn [7] employed the equivalent inclusion method to resolve the closed form of the energy release rate for a permeable elliptical crack in a transversely isotropic piezoelectric solid simultaneously subjected to the antiplane shear stress (mode III) and the in-plane electric loading actuated in perpendicular with crack faces.

However, piezoelectric cracked materials obviously contain randomly aligned multiply cracks and, frequently, the crack density is extremely high. Therefore, more closely examining the averaging electroelastic response and effective electroelastic moduli is highly desired. Moreover, a fracture study must be performed of a piezoelectric solid containing multiply permeable elliptical cracks subjected to mechanical loads in modes I, II, and III as well as an anti-plane electric field, in-plane electric field incited in parallel or perpendicular with crack faces. Accomplishing such a task would allow us to fully exploit the merits of piezoelectric materials. Therefore, in this study, we present the closed forms of the energy release rates for multiply permeable elliptical cracks involved in an infinite piezoelectric solid, which is solely subjected to either one of three kinds of mechanical loading or one of three kinds of electric loading.

BASIC EQUATIONS

Consider an infinitely extended piezoelectric composite D containing an ellipsoidal inclusion Ω whose material properties are the same as the matrix. Let Z_{Mn}^* represent eigenstrain (or stress-free transformation strain ϵ_{mn}^* when $M \leq 3$), and eigenelectric field (or electric displacement-free electric field $-E_n^*$ when $M = 4$) in the inclusion Ω , and zero in the matrix $D - \Omega$. Herein the lowercase subscripts range from 1 to 3, while the uppercase subscripts range from 1 to 4. When Z_{Mn}^* is uniformly distributed in Ω , Huang and Yu [10] indicated that the strain ϵ_{mn} and electric field E_n due to the uniform eigenfield inside the inclusion are also uniform and have the unified form:

$$Z_{Mn} = \begin{cases} \epsilon_{mn} = S_{mAb} Z_{Ab}^* & M \leq 3, \\ -E_n = S_{4nAb} Z_{Ab}^* & M = 4, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where

$$S_{MnAb} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{8\pi} L_{iJAb} (\bar{G}_{mJin} + \bar{G}_{nJim}) & M \leq 3, \\ \frac{1}{4\pi} L_{iJAb} \bar{G}_{4Jin} & M = 4, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

are referred to as the electroelastic Eshelby tensors [10] analogous to Eshelby [9] tensor for elastic inclusion problems. In the preceding equation, L_{iJMn} denotes the electro-elastic stiffness tensor for the matrix and has defined by

$$L_{iJMn} = \begin{cases} C_{ijmn} & J, M \leq 3, \\ e_{nij} & J \leq 3; M = 4, \\ e_{imn} & J = 4; M \leq 3, \\ -\kappa_{in} & J, M = 4, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where \bar{G}_{MJin} is defined by [10]

$$\bar{G}_{MJin} = \int_{-1}^1 \int_0^{2\pi} N_{MJ}(\bar{\xi}) D^{-1}(\bar{\xi}) \bar{\xi}_i \bar{\xi}_n d\theta d\bar{\zeta}_3, \quad (4)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 \bar{\xi}_1 &= \zeta_1, & a_2 \bar{\xi}_2 &= \zeta_2, & a_3 \bar{\xi}_3 &= \zeta_3, \\ \zeta_1/\zeta &= \bar{\zeta}_1, & \zeta_2/\zeta &= \bar{\zeta}_2, & \zeta_3/\zeta &= \bar{\zeta}_3, & \zeta &= (\zeta_1^2 + \zeta_2^2 + \zeta_3^2)^{1/2}, \\ \bar{\zeta}_1 &= (1 - \bar{\zeta}_3^2)^{1/2} \cos\theta, & \bar{\zeta}_2 &= (1 - \bar{\zeta}_3^2)^{1/2} \sin\theta, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where a_1 , a_2 , and a_3 are the lengths of the semiaxes of the ellipsoid, and $N_{MJ}(\bar{\xi})$ and $D(\bar{\xi})$ represent the cofactor and the determinant of the 4×4 matrix $[L_{iJMn} \bar{\xi}_i \bar{\xi}_n]$. In Eqn 3, C_{ijmn} is elastic moduli, e_{nij} represents the piezoelectric coefficient, and κ_{in} denotes the dielectric constant. In this work, the electric potential and normal component of the electric displacement of a permeable crack are continuous across the crack surfaces. These surfaces are modeled as an elliptical inclusion oriented with its generatrix parallel to x_3 axis.

The stress and electric displacement, Σ_{iJ} , in the inclusion caused by Z_{Mn}^* uniformly distribution in Ω can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{iJ} &= L_{iJMn} (Z_{Mn} - Z_{Mn}^*) \\ &= \begin{cases} \sigma_{ij} = C_{ijmn} (\epsilon_{mn} - \epsilon_{mn}^*) - e_{nij} (E_n - E_n^*), & J \leq 3, \\ D_i = e_{imn} (\epsilon_{mn} - \epsilon_{mn}^*) + \kappa_{in} (E_n - E_n^*), & J = 4, \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where ϵ_{mn} , σ_{ij} , E_n , and D_i denote the strain, stress, electric field, and electric displacement, respectively.

EQUIVALENT INCLUSION METHOD FOR CRACK PROBLEMS

Consider a sufficiently large piezoelectric material D which contains equal shaped, randomly distributed, and identically oriented ellipsoidal inhomogeneities Ω ($=\Omega_1 + \Omega_2 + \dots + \Omega_N$) with electroelastic moduli L_{iJMn}^* and volume fraction f . The surrounding piezoelectric matrix is denoted by $D-\Omega$ and has an electroelastic moduli L_{iJMn} . As generally known, the inhomogeneities are randomly distributed and are of the same shape, accounting why this study considers only one representative volume V which contains only an isolated inhomogeneity. Let the shape of the representative volume resemble that of the inhomogeneity. Assume that the material is subjected to the far-field traction and electric displacement, $\Sigma_{ij}^0 n_i$, on the boundary with the outward unit normal vector n_i . If no inhomogeneity exists, the strain and electric field, Z_{Mn}^0 , distribute uniformly over the entire domain. Notably, inhomogeneities provides disturbance in local fields of both the matrix and inhomogeneities. Let Σ_{ij}^m and Σ_{ij}^Ω denote the local disturbances of the stress and electric displacement in the matrix and inhomogeneities, respectively. The averages of these quantities are denoted $\bar{\Sigma}_{ij}^m$ and $\bar{\Sigma}_{ij}^\Omega$ for the matrix and inhomogeneities, respectively. The fact that the average of the stress and electric displacement disturbance must be zero leads to

$$(1-f)\bar{\Sigma}_{ij}^m + f\bar{\Sigma}_{ij}^\Omega = 0. \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the average disturbed stress and electric displacement in the matrix and the k th inhomogeneity can be written as

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{ij}^m = L_{iJMn} \bar{Z}_{Mn}^m \quad \text{in } D-\Omega, \quad (8)$$

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{ij}^{\Omega_k} = L_{iJMn}^* (\bar{Z}_{Mn}^m + \bar{Z}_{Mn}^k) \quad \text{in } \Omega_k, \quad (9)$$

where \bar{Z}_{Mn}^m represent the average strain and electric field in the matrix. Restated, \bar{Z}_{Mn}^m considers the interaction between neighboring representative volumes. In Eqn 9, \bar{Z}_{Mn}^k denotes the average disturbance of the otherwise uniform strain and electric field in Ω_k .

The fact that all inhomogeneities are of the same shape with the same material properties accounts for why the average value over Ω_k is identical with that over all inhomogeneities, i.e. $\bar{\Sigma}_{ij}^{\Omega_k} = \bar{\Sigma}_{ij}^\Omega$. Consequently, the average stress and electric displacement in the inhomogeneities can be expressed as

$$\Sigma_{ij}^0 + \bar{\Sigma}_{ij}^\Omega = L_{iJMn}^* (Z_{Mn}^0 + \bar{Z}_{Mn}^m + \bar{Z}_{Mn}^k). \quad (10)$$

According to the equivalent inclusion method, the stress and electric displacement in an inhomogeneity can be simulated by those in an equivalent inclusion with the electroelastic constants of the matrix and a fictitious eigenfield, i.e. Z_{Mn}^* . Therefore, Ean 10 can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{ij}^0 + \bar{\Sigma}_{ij}^\Omega &= L_{iJMn}^* (Z_{Mn}^0 + \bar{Z}_{Mn}^m + \bar{Z}_{Mn}^k) \\ &= L_{iJMn} (Z_{Mn}^0 + \bar{Z}_{Mn}^m + \bar{Z}_{Mn}^k - Z_{Mn}^*). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Since the applied loads are uniform and the inhomogeneity is an ellipsoid, \bar{Z}_{Mn} is also uniform in the inhomogeneities [10]. It can also be related to the fictitious eigenfield Z_{Mn}^* by

$$\bar{Z}_{Mn} = S_{MnAb} Z_{Ab}^*, \quad (12)$$

where S_{MnAb} denotes the electroelastic Eshelby tensor and has been defined in Eqn 2. By substituting Eqn 12 into Eqn 11, the average disturbances of stress and electric displacement in the inhomogeneities become

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{iJ}^{\Omega} = L_{iJMn} \bar{Z}_{Mn}^m + L_{iJMn} (S_{MnAb} - I_{MnAb}) Z_{Ab}^*, \quad (13)$$

where the shorthand notation I_{MnAb} represents the second order and fourth order identity tensors, respectively:

$$I_{MnAb} = \begin{cases} (\delta_{ma} \delta_{nb} + \delta_{mb} \delta_{na}) / 2 & M, A \leq 3, \\ \delta_{nb} & M = A = 4, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Combining Eqn 7, Eqn 9 and Eqn 13 leads to

$$\bar{Z}_{Mn}^m = -f (S_{MnAb} - I_{MnAb}) Z_{Ab}^*. \quad (15)$$

Substituting Eqn 15 into Eqn 8 and Eqn 13, respectively, yields

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{iJ}^m = -f L_{iJMn} (S_{MnAb} - I_{MnAb}) Z_{Ab}^*, \quad (16)$$

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{iJ}^{\Omega} = (1 - f) L_{iJMn} (S_{MnAb} - I_{MnAb}) Z_{Ab}^*, \quad (17)$$

in which some dummy indices have been properly altered. The equivalent eigenstrain and eigenelectric field, Z_{Ab}^* , are solved by substituting Eqn 15 into the equivalency condition Eqn 11. Thus, we have

$$h_{iJMn} Z_{Mn}^* = H_{iJnM} \Sigma_{nM}^0 \quad (18)$$

where

$$h_{iJMn} = (L_{iJAb}^* - L_{iJAb}) [(1 - f) S_{AbMn} + f I_{AbMn}] + L_{iJMn}, \quad (19)$$

$$H_{iJnM} = I_{iJnM} - L_{iJAb}^* L_{AbnM}^{-1}. \quad (20)$$

If cracks are treated as the inhomogeneities in which their elastic moduli and piezoelectric constants vanish while dielectric constants κ_{in}^* are remained finite, then h_{iJMn} and H_{iJnM} can be obtained explicitly.

ENERGY RELEASE RATES

Determining the crack extension force G requires calculating the change of total potential energy when the crack extends by the amount Δa_1 . When the far-field surface traction and

electric flux density, Σ_{ij}^0 , are applied on the boundary of the material, the change of total potential energy for the cracked piezoelectric solid is defined as follows.

$$\Delta W = -\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \Sigma_{ij}^0 Z_{ji}^* d\mathbf{x} = -\frac{1}{2} (2\pi a_1 a_2) \Sigma_{ij}^0 Z_{ji}^*, \quad (21)$$

where $2\pi a_1 a_2$ is the volume per unit thickness of the elliptical crack. The above equation can be flexibly used to calculate the change of the total potential energy since it simply involves the applied electromechanical loads and the equivalent eigenfields.

The energy release rate per unit thickness for an infinitesimal crack extension can be defined as

$$G = -\frac{\partial \Delta W}{\partial a_1}. \quad (22)$$

Substituting Z_{Mn}^* listed in Appendix B into the foregoing equation leads to

$$G_{21} = \frac{4(a_1 + a_2)C_{11}\pi\sigma_{21}^0{}^2}{(C_{11}{}^2 - C_{12}{}^2)(1-f)}, \quad (23)$$

which is the energy release rate for the in-plane shear stress applied in the sufficiently large piezoelectric material domain. Similarly,

$$G_{22} = \{A_0(a_2 A_2 + 4A_0 a_1 C_{11})(1-f) + [4A_0 a_1 A_1 C_{11} f + a_2(A_3 + A_1 A_2 f)] \kappa_{11}^*\} \pi \sigma_{22}^0{}^2 / \{A_0(C_{11}^2 - C_{12}^2)(1-f)[A_0(1-f) + A_1 f \kappa_{11}^*]\}, \quad (24)$$

and

$$G_{23} = a_2(B_1 f - B_2) \{a_2(2a_1 + a_2)B_0(1-f) + C_{44}[a_1^2 + a_2(2a_1 + a_2)f] \kappa_{11}^*\} \pi \sigma_{23}^0{}^2 / \{B_0(1-f)[a_2 B_0(1-f) + C_{44}(a_1 + a_2 f) \kappa_{11}^*]^2\} \quad (25)$$

represent energy release rates for the tensile stress applied and the anti-plane shear stress applied, respectively. Following the same procedures as the above derivations for in-plane electric loading incited in parallel with crack faces, we have

$$G_{14} = -\{a_2 C_{44}[e_{15}^2 + C_{44}(\kappa_{11} - \kappa_{11}^*)][2a_1 a_2 C_{44} \kappa_{11}^* + a_2^2 C_{44} \kappa_{11}^* + a_1^2(B_0 - B_0 f + C_{44} f \kappa_{11}^*)] \pi D_1^0{}^2\} / \{B_0[a_2 C_{44} \kappa_{11}^* + a_1(B_0 - B_0 f + C_{44} f \kappa_{11}^*)]^2\}. \quad (26)$$

For in-plane electric loading incited in perpendicular with crack faces,

$$G_{24} = -\{a_2 C_{44}[e_{15}^2 + C_{44}(\kappa_{11} - \kappa_{11}^*)][a_2(2a_1 + a_2)B_0(-1+f) + C_{44}[a_1^2 + a_2(2a_1 + a_2)f] \kappa_{11}^*] \pi D_2^0{}^2\} / \{B_0[a_2 B_0(-1+f) - C_{44}(a_1 + a_2 f) \kappa_{11}^*]^2\}. \quad (27)$$

For anti-plane electric loading incited in parallel with crack faces,

$$G_{34} = \frac{-A_1 a_2 (A_0 - A_1 \kappa_{11}^*) \pi D_3^0}{A_0^2 (1-f) + A_0 A_1 f \kappa_{11}^*}. \quad (28)$$

The coefficients $A_0 \sim A_3$ and $B_0 \sim B_2$ appearing in preceding equations are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A_0 &= [2C_{33}e_{31}^2 - 4C_{13}e_{31}e_{33} + (C_{11} + C_{12})e_{33}^2 - 2C_{13}^2\kappa_{33} + (C_{11} + C_{12})C_{33}\kappa_{33}], \\ A_1 &= -2C_{13}^2 + C_{11}C_{33} + C_{12}C_{33}, \\ A_2 &= (C_{11} + C_{12})[-2C_{13}e_{31}e_{33} + C_{11}e_{33}^2 - C_{13}^2\kappa_{33} + C_{33}(e_{31}^2 + C_{11}\kappa_{33})], \\ A_3 &= (C_{11} - C_{12})(C_{11} + C_{12})(C_{33}e_{31} - C_{13}e_{33})^2, \\ B_0 &= e_{15}^2 + C_{44}\kappa_{11}, \quad B_1 = \kappa_{11}[e_{15}^2 + C_{44}(\kappa_{11} - \kappa_{11}^*)], \\ B_2 &= [C_{44}\kappa_{11}(\kappa_{11} + a\kappa_{11}^*) + e_{15}^2(\kappa_{11} + \kappa_{11}^* + a\kappa_{11}^*)]. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Eqn 23~ Eqn 25 are the closed forms of the energy release rates for an elliptical permeable crack embedded in an infinite piezoelectric solid under distinct types of mechanical loading. Correspondingly, when subjected to different types of electric loading, the closed forms of the release rates for the crack are represented in Eqn 26~ Eqn 28. As a numerical example for reflecting the physical dimension of these closed forms for the release rate, lead zirconate titanate (PTZ-5H) piezoceramic is illustrated. Its material properties are represented as follows [4].

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11} &= 126 \text{ GPa}, \quad C_{12} = 55 \text{ GPa}, \quad C_{13} = 53 \text{ GPa}, \\ C_{33} &= 117 \text{ GPa}, \quad C_{44} = 35.3 \text{ GPa}, \\ e_{31} &= -6.5 \text{ C/m}^2, \quad e_{33} = 23.3 \text{ C/m}^2, \quad e_{15} = 17 \text{ C/m}^2, \\ \kappa_{11} &= 1.51 \times 10^{-8} \text{ C/Vm}, \quad \kappa_{33} = 1.30 \times 10^{-8} \text{ C/Vm}, \quad \kappa_{11}^* = 8.85 \times 10^{-12} \text{ C/Vm}, \\ \sigma_{21}^0 &= \sigma_{22}^0 = \sigma_{23}^0 = 0.5 \text{ GPa}, \quad D_1^0 = D_2^0 = D_3^0 = 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ C/m}^2, \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

where *GPa* denotes the giganewtons per square meter, *C* represents the charge in coulombs, and *V* is the electric potential in volts.

According to the numerical results, Fig. 1 reveals that the energy release rate monotonously increases with respect to the extension of the aspect ratio (a_1/a_2) of the random distributed and identical oriented elliptical cracks under mechanical loading applied and 2% cracks volume fraction, which coincides with the conventional fracture criterion. This figure also indicates that the in-plane shear stress and tensile stress applied in multiply cracked piezoelectric material are extremely sensitive in terms of propagating the dilation of the elliptical cracks in contrast to the anti-plane shear stress. Fig. 2 depicts how the aspect ratio of the elliptical cracks influences the energy release rates for three distinct senses of electric loading. According to this figure, the minus values of the energy release rate suggest that the electric loading can diminish the dilation of the elliptical flaw. This figure also reveals that in comparison with the other two types of electric loading, the in-plane electric loading incited in perpendicular with permeable crack faces not only has a tremendous effect in terms of retarding the expansion of the cracks, but also the retarding effect augments with respect to the extension of crack faces. Also of relevant interest is to examine how permeable cracks volume fraction influence the energy release rate either subjected to different types of mechanical loading or distinct sense of electric fields. As Fig. 3 depicts, the energy release rates increase proportionally to the amplification of cracks volume fraction for three different

mechanical loading. In addition, the anti-shear stress still slightly influences the propagation for those cracks. Fig. 4 displays the increment of the volume fraction of the elliptical cracks on energy release rates for three distinct senses of electric loading with the negative values of the energy release rate.

CONCLUSIONS

This work presents fracture criteria in closed forms for an infinite piezoelectric solid with multiply permeable elliptical cracks separately subjected to three modes of mechanical loading and three forms of electric loading. The energy release rates are introduced herein to quantitatively determine the crack's extension force. According to our results, the closed forms for energy release rates are a function of the aspect ratio of the crack, the type of the electromechanical loading, the volume fraction of elliptical cracks, and the piezoelectric properties. Results presented herein for multiply permeable elliptical cracks containing in a piezoelectric solid subjected to one of the electromechanical loading can hopefully be extended to resolve permeable cracks simultaneously subjected to mechanical loading and electrical loading. Moreover, fracture mechanics of the multiply cracked material should be considered during the design process of sensor and actuator applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank the National Science Council of the Republic of China for financially supporting this research under contracts NSC 87-2216-E-035-016 (JHH) and NSC 88-2611-E-0006-003 (HCK)

REFERENCES

1. Parton, V. Z., "Fracture Mechanics of Piezoelectric Materials," *Acta Astronaut*, Vol.3, pp.671-683 (1976).
2. Deeg, W. F., *The Analysis of Dislocation, Cracks, and Inclusion Problems in Piezoelectric Solids*, Ph.D. dissertation, Stanford University (1980).
3. Pak, Y. E., "Crack Extension Force in a Piezoelectric Material", *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol.112, pp.647-653 (1990).
4. Pak, Y. E., "Circular Inclusion Problem in Antiplane Piezoelectricity," *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol.29, pp.2403-2419 (1992).
5. Suo, Z., Kuo, C.M., Barnett, D.M., and Willis, J.R., "Fracture Mechanics for Piezoelectric Ceramics," *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol. 40, pp.739-765 (1992).
6. Sosa, H., "On the fracture Mechanics of Piezoelectric solids," *Int. J. Solids Structures*, Vol. 29, pp2613-2622 (1992).
7. Dunn, M. L., "The Effects of Crack Face Boundary Conditions on the Fracture Mechanics of Piezoelectric Solids," *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol.48, No.1, pp.25-39 (1994).
8. Mura, T., *Micromechanics of Defects in Solids*, second, revised edition, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers (1987).
9. Eshelby, J. D., "The Determination of the Elastic Field of an Ellipsoidal Inclusion, and Related Problems," *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London*, Vol.A241, pp.376-396 (1957).

10. Huang, J. H. and Yu, J. S., "Electroelastic Eshelby's Tensors for an Ellipsoidal Piezoelectric Inclusion," *Composite Engineering*, Vol.4, No.11, pp.1169-1182 (1994).
11. Griffith, A.A., "The phenomena of rupture and flow in solid," *Transactions of the Royal Society*, A221, pp.163-179 (1921).

Fig. 2: The effect of aspect ratio of elliptical cracks in energy release rates of PTZ-5H piezoceramic with cracks volume fraction, $f = 0.002$, subjected to three kinds of mechanical loading.

Fig. 2: The effect of aspect ratio of elliptical cracks in energy release rates of PTZ-5H piezoceramic with cracks volume fraction, $f = 0.002$, incited in three types of electric fields.

Fig. 3: Energy release rates variation on cracks volume fraction with crack aspect ratio, $a_1/a_2 = 300$, under three distinct mechanical loads applied.

Fig. 4: Energy release rates variation on cracks volume fraction with crack aspect ratio, $a_1/a_2 = 300$, under three variant electrical fields incited.